

Seed bank dynamics of ant-dispersed Australian Acacias in the Fynbos biome

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Introduction

- South Africa has approximately 201 alien species, covering 1.7 million ha [1].
- Australian *Acacias* most prominent, covering > 700 000 ha [1].
- Fynbos biome most heavily invaded by Australian *Acacia* [1,2].
- Australian *Acacia* clearing costs total 815.6 million rand [3].
- Australian *Acacia* seed banks prevent effective and sustainable removal [4].
- Seed banks enable Australian *Acacia* to survive in time and space and to re-establish [5].
- Seed banks decrease clearing effectiveness and increases costs.
- Ant dispersed species, *A. saligna*, *A. longifolia*, *A. mearnsii*, and *A. pycnantha*, accumulate largest seed banks and therefore are greatest obstacle for managers.

Knowledge Gap

- General lack of knowledge on Australian *Acacia* seed bank dynamics (Table 1), despite significance.
- Existing data collected in isolation or used different sampling methods - difficult to extrapolate and often of little practical value.
- Not unique in global context - few studies on seed bank dynamics of alien plants done [6].

Figure 1: Photos illustrating the growth habit of a) *A. saligna*, b) *A. pycnantha*, c) *A. longifolia* and d) *A. mearnsii*.

Table 1: Seed production, % inflorescences bearing pods, % seeds lost to predation, viability of fresh and soil stored seed, dormancy of fresh and soil stored seed, seed rain, % seed actively dispersed (e.g. by ants) and seed bank densities of *A. saligna*, *A. longifolia*, *A. pycnantha* and *A. mearnsii* in South Africa.

Species	Seed Production /m ²	Inflorescences bearing Pods %	Predation %*	Seed Aborted %	Viability Fresh %	Dormancy %	Seed rain /m ²	Predation % [#]	% Active Dispersal	Seed Bank /m ²	Decay %	Viability Soil %	Reference
<i>A. saligna</i>	-	-	-	-	-	82 - 94	-	-	-	-	-	-	9
	10 562	10 – 23	-	-	-	96.4	530 - 5 443	-	-	145 - 11 920	-	99	11
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7 920 – 45 800	-	86 – 100	3
	-	-	-	-	100	89.6	-	-	-	-	45	-	4
	-	-	-	-	-	-	2100	31	94	7 920	-	-	5, 6
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	68	-	-	-	10
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2 000 - 212 000	-	-	12
	-	-	-	-	-	-	446 - 13 472	-	-	-	-	-	19
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	14 880 – 26 560	-	-	18
	-	-	0.3 - 42.1	-	-	-	286 - 13 627	-	-	-	137 - 37 316	-	90 – 100
<i>A. longifolia</i>	-	-	-	-	98	97	-	-	-	-	-	-	8
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	715 - 8097	-	-	7
	-	11 – 34	-	-	-	98	2 923	-	-	7 646	-	98.5	11
	-	-	95 – 99	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2 078 - 3 473	-	99	15
<i>A. mearnsii</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	11 500	-	-	34 000	-	-	13
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3912 - 4528	-	99	2
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	34	57	-	-	-	16
<i>A. pycnantha</i>	-	-	-	-	97.5 - 100	100	-	-	-	38 340	-	-	11
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5314	-	-	14

* Pre-dispersal Predation; # Post – Dispersal Predation

1: Dennil, 1985; 2: Fourie, 2008; 3: Holmes et al., 1987; 4: Holmes, 1989a; 5: Holmes, 1990a; 6: Holmes, 1990b; 7: Holmes, 2002; 8: Jeffery et al., 1988; 9: Jones, 1963; 10: Midgeley and Bond, 1995; 11: Milton and Hall, 1981; 12: Morris, 1997; 13: Pieterse, 1987; 14: Pieterse, 1997; 15: Pieterse and Cairns, 1986; 16: Pieterse and Cairns, 1990; 17: Strydom, 2012; 18: Strydom et al., 2012; 19: Wood and Morris, 2007

Figure 2: Simplistic model illustrating seed bank dynamics. Adapted from Simpson *et al.*, (1989)

Rationale

- Four illustrated phases (Figure 2) and associated mortality factors will be studied for *A. mearnsii*, *A. saligna*, *A. longifolia* and *A. pycnantha*.
- Give an understanding of the number of seeds that will have to be managed, the stage during which their seeds are most vulnerable, whether this loss is significant and if this is consistent between individuals of different ages and populations situated in different environments.
- Indicate whether any generalities can be made between species with regards to their seed bank dynamics.

Methodology

- Six sites for each species.
- Annual seed crop size will be estimated. Additionally tree height, circumference, mean canopy diameter, gall load, pre-dispersal seed loss (abortion, parasitism etc.), seed viability and dormancy will be determined.
- Seed survival over time, primary dispersal, post-dispersal parasitism and secondary dispersal will be examined.
- Number of seeds in seed bank will be estimated.
- Seed decay and germination of seeds will be investigated.
- Seed bank dynamic models for each species will be developed.

References

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